

STRUCTURE OF AN INTEGRATIVE APPROACH TO TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract: In this thesis, the relevance of the integral approach and its functions are based, the components of the structure of the integral approach are presented. Aspects, functions, principles and goals of an integrative approach to foreign language teaching are distinguished. The author also describes methods that can be used in foreign language teaching based on an integrative approach.

Key words: integrative approach, foreign language teaching, methods, professional activity, methodological approach, didactic principle, curriculum, pedagogical skills.

Introduction:

One of the main units of updating the educational content is the concept of integration. It is the integrative nature of a person, in other words, the personal qualities of a future specialist - knowledge. It represents skills, practical experience, abilities, value orientations. An interactive approach ensures and strengthens readiness for professional activity.

The fundamental reforms implemented in our republic are the selection of a unique socio-political and economic development path in society, as well as the concept of the development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030, the strategic goals and priorities of the development of higher education, tasks, determines its stages in the medium and long term and is the basis for the development of programs and complex measures related to the sector [1].

In the concept of the development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030, improving the quality of education, training competitive personnel based on ensuring the strong integration of science, education and production based on the needs of the social sphere and economic sectors of the higher education system, effective organization of scientific and innovative activities, students' independent education, critical and creative thinking, systematic analysis, formation of entrepreneurial skills, introduction of methodologies and technologies aimed at strengthening competencies in the educational process, educational directing the process to the formation of practical skills, in this regard, the tasks of wide introduction of advanced pedagogical technologies, educational programs and teaching-methodical materials based on international educational standards into the educational process have been put forward.

Currently, changes are taking place in the education system: it will be oriented towards entering the world education space. One of the most important trends in the development of higher education of the 21st century is the strengthening of integration processes at all levels, from personal to international. Integration is one of the most important innovative phenomena in education today. It surpasses all other phenomena "in terms of breadth of experimental embodiment, depth of creative design, continuity and dialectic of historical

development" [2, 26]. The main task of integration processes is to achieve synergistic effects on the basis of collaboration and cooperation, which prevails over differentiation and isolation. Integration processes lead to the formation of new elements, change, make existing ones more effective.

Globalization processes, changes in all spheres of human activity are changing the requirements of higher professional education. The educational system must meet the new demands of society. As a rule, the teacher only teaches his subject separately from others. But this approach does not form a set of knowledge that students need to acquire for successful professional activity.

Discussion: Issues such as the theoretical foundations, principles, approach to integration, directions of integration, integrative programs, integrative lessons, and the creation of an integrated course model are the most important pedagogical problems awaiting their solution.

Professor N.N.Azizkhodzhaeva conducted research on the problems of applying pedagogical technologies to the educational process and improving pedagogical skills, emphasizing in her research that teaching technologies in the vocational education system ensure the assimilation of fundamental and practical knowledge [2, 190-p].

O.K. Tolipov conducted research on the topic "Pedagogical technologies for the development of general labor and professional skills and qualifications in the system of higher pedagogical education", and the role of pedagogical technologies in the development of professional skills and qualifications in students and its application to the educational process. studied the important aspects of application [8, 45-p].

D. O. Khimmataliev's research highlighted the uniqueness of the technological approach in the future teacher's professional training and pedagogical activity [9, 92-p].

Yu.K.Babansky made a great contribution to the development of the collective approach, he claims that the collective planning of tasks plays the role of optimization methods, the collective approach to the selection of educational content not only takes into account different activity methods, but also the repetition of materials also envisages interdisciplinary orientation that helps to eliminate.

Theoretical, philosophical, psychological-pedagogical, methodical foundations of integration Ye.N.Kabanova-Meller, Yu.A.Samarina. S. L. Rubinstein, S. E. Kamensky, I. D. Zverev, V. N. Maksimova. It is covered in the works of such scientists as G. Spencer, M. G. Chepikov, N. K. Chapaev, R. G. Safarova, R. SH. Akhldinov, UD. Musaev, I. V. Makukhina, P. Musaev, M. G. Nishonbaeva, M. Kh. Lutfullaev, M. Jumaniyozova.

In the research works of Nishonaliev, A.I.Avazboev, O.A.Abduquddusov, the organization of teaching within the framework of integrative knowledge is scientifically based. Intersubject integration I.D. Zverev, V.N. Maksimova, M.G. Chepikov, N.K. Chapaev, B.D. Komissarov on theoretical and methodological bases, content, structure of ensuring integration of subjects and pedagogical integration; B.M. Mirzakhmedov, Yu.G. Makhmudov about the integrative approach to the implementation of technical education in physics teaching, M. Jumaniyozova about the integration of physics and astronomy sciences; E. O. Turdikulov, S. M. Fayzullaev, M. G. Nishonbaeva on ecological education for students (physical and biological foundations of ecological education) by teaching based on the integrative content of natural sciences; A.R. Khodzhaboev, U.Nishonaliev, R.Choriev on the problem of integration in higher and vocational education A.A. Abdukadirov, M.Kh. Lutfullaev, U.SH. Begimkulov Integrating and improving

the educational process in higher education with the help of information technologies scientific and research works have been carried out [8, 66-p].

The integrative approach works in harmony and connection with didactic principles (scientific, polytechnic, professional orientation, regularity, systematicity, coherence, comprehensibility, instruction, classification).

In many cases, the integrative approach allows us to imagine the object under study as a whole system, a complete and clear implementation of the above-mentioned principles in some sense.

Integration of the content of the educational material as a didactic process is a multidimensional, multifaceted, system-like research object, and its analysis requires a systematic and structured approach. Because it is intended to study its features such as composition, function, structure.

The application of the dialectical analysis method in the learning process requires knowledge to move from cause to effect, from simple to complex, from coincidence to necessity or vice versa. Thus, in a word, the highest point of analysis is a whole object.

As a result of synthesis, the highest level of dialectical analysis is created.

Integrating (combining, generalizing, rounding up) is essentially the task of synthesis, which restores such aspects as the internal connection, unity, and relations of the studied object. In this way, we get an idea about the change and development of the object.

Integration is manifested mainly as a means of theoretical synthesis between academic subjects and as an interdisciplinary synthesis, and directly involves the creation of general scientific knowledge.

Integrative processes take into account a kind of interdependent model of several tasks, directions, aspirations, different levels and concrete forms in the process of continuous education.

A.L. Chekin in his monograph "Higher education: an integrative approach" focused on the main aspects of integration in the educational process, separated and analyzed the integrative components, showed the possibilities of their implementation "as a catalyst for the efficiency of the proportional process" [11].

In the scientific research conducted by experienced scientists in the field of improving the pedagogical skills of the teacher, various opinions are expressed about the development of pedagogical skills, and the main reserve of this process is the constant striving of the teacher to analyze his pedagogical activity in educational institutions, improvement of his reflexive abilities, since the development of the reflexive approach depends on the specific pedagogical reflection, connecting it with the formation of pedagogical thinking, thus it is possible to develop the teacher's pedagogical reflection they emphasize.

Looking at the analysis of professional pedagogical activity and self-analysis as a set of pedagogical skills aimed at solving pedagogical tasks in order to correct and improve them from the point of view of the teacher's activity and reflexive approach, A.V. Khristeva combined the system of analytical skills with the system of analytical activity relates [10, 71-p].

Stages of analysis and self-analysis of professional pedagogical activity according to the teaching of A. V. Khristeva:

1. Content - diagnostic (preparation - adaptation) stage;
2. Purposeful design (clarification of purpose from analysis and self-analysis) stage;

3. Technological (professional pedagogical process and self-analysis) stage;

4. The theoretical stage of analysis and self-analysis (theoretical understanding of the causes and consequences of the relationship between the essence and results of pedagogical activity and the process of pedagogical activity);

5. Reflexive assessment of activity (activity assessment and reflexive analysis) stage;

1. Correction (creative stage, improvement of one's own pedagogical activity based on theoretical understanding and assessment and determining ways and methods of creative use of effective pedagogical experiences of colleagues).

Today's innovative pedagogical activity is also noteworthy for its selection and research characteristics. Therefore, the important direction of the activities of the leaders of pedagogical teams, methodical employees of scientific research institutes is the analysis and evaluation of innovations created by teachers, the creation of necessary conditions for the creation and application of their effectiveness.

Analysis of the problems of formation of professional competence of students, as well as identification of separate components of professional competence necessary for professional activity (and subsequent assessment criteria) required solving the essence of the concept of "competence". The term "competence" is derived from the Latin word "competens", which means capable:

- 1) having competencies;
- 2) knowledgeable in a certain field.

At the same time, the concept of "competence" is closely related to the concept of "competence". The analysis of modern references and scientific-pedagogical literature on the research problem allowed us to identify two similar confusions, such as "competence", which at first glance are different and used in the same sense.

D. I. Ushakov tried to show the difference between competence and competencies: competence - awareness, authority; competence - knowledge, experience of a person". In the Encyclopedia Britannica, the term "competence" is interpreted as the knowledge and skills acquired by a person.

According to O. M. Mutovkina, "authority" is a secondary concept derived from "competence" and "competence" and means the scope of application of knowledge, skills and abilities of a person, while "competence" reflects their internal commonality.

To justify our approach, we refer to the works of I.A.Zimnaya, A.V.Khutorsky and others, in particular, I.A.Zimnaya defines competences as follows: "internal potential, hidden psychological derivatives: the sum of knowledge, ideas, actions, attitudes" [14, p. 35]. A.V. Khutorsky states that competencies are a set of educational preparation, skills, and personal qualities.

The teacher's target competence includes the ability to set various goals. The purpose of professional training is directed to the formation of technological culture in young people, determines the content of the educational process, and serves as a criterion for evaluating the acquired knowledge and abilities.

Content competence consists of the ability to determine the content of education, training and development at each of the stages of professional training. The importance of the content of education is determined by the normative documents considered as the state educational standard.

The monitoring competence of the educator describes the ability of the educator to support the re-dependence (control problem) and the comparison of the actual results with the planned ones, that is, to ensure the quality of education.

Communicative competence describes the features of the pedagogue's communicative activity, the uniqueness of his interaction with future vocational education pedagogues. Emphasis is placed on the communication link with the effectiveness of pedagogical activity aimed at achieving didactic (educational and educational) goals. Communicative competence includes methods that help to achieve high-level communication.

1. Social competence is an indicator of the social importance of increasing the level of methodical training, the ability to assume responsibility for the proposed new methodical approaches and their application, specific future professional education of personal interests, educational institution, society is a manifestation of the need.

According to many scientists professional competences of students should be based on the development of integral and analytical abilities. In this regard, one of the goals of our research was to create pedagogical conditions for the development of professional competence of students, to take into account the possibility of their change in the future professional activity.

Researchers of the competent approach define the cognitive activity of students with a certain orientation as the main condition for the formation of competence. Cognitive activity allows acquiring knowledge methods that help to collect information, focus on intellectual development and gain professional competence.

Thus, the concept of competence combines not only cognitive and operational-technological components of future engineers, but also motivational, moral, social and behavioral components. In addition, we connected the justification of the formed competences and professional competence with the educational content of preparing students for professional activities, because the competences are acquired in the educational process.

The use of a competent approach is based on having a high level of professional competence, basic technical and technological education, an emotional and valuable attitude to any type of activity, professional-innovative activity.

Thus, the need to develop a methodological model from the point of view of a competent approach has set the task of critically reviewing the existing practice of preparing students for professional and innovative activities and determining the readiness of students for professional activities.

The above-mentioned pedagogical values are divided into personal and instrumental aspects, which include social and professional components and differ according to their content.

Personal values are purposeful values that include the creative description of a teacher's work, prestige, social significance, responsibility to the state, the opportunity for self-expression, love and care for children. Values of this type serve as a basis for the development of teachers and learners. Target values appear as decisive axiological functions in the system of other pedagogical values, because its purpose reflects the main content of the teacher's activity.

Therefore, new approaches to learning are needed. Scientists have confirmed the need to create fundamental pedagogical structures, whose task is to form a general culture of

students, prepare them for successful professional activity and develop a holistic worldview. An integrative approach formed in domestic and foreign methodology seems to be the most efficient and effective in this regard. It can solve the problem of holistic training of future specialists due to the integration of not only disciplines, but also the methods, forms and organization of the educational process. As V. F. Tenishcheva rightly noted, "integration ensures the transition to a more integrated pedagogical system and, as a result, leads to an increase in the level of the educational process, which is reflected in the formation of the necessary competencies of students" [4, p. 69].

According to I. A. Zimniy and E. V. Zemtsova, the integrative approach is "a holistic representation of a complex of objects, events, processes united by at least one characteristic by society, as a result of which its new quality is created" [14, 84-p].

Thus, the review of the structure of the integrated approach to teaching a foreign language includes aspects, principles, goals and results. Consider the components of an integrative approach: methodological, organizational and activity and content.

The methodological aspect includes the integration of teaching methods of different subjects. For example, pedagogical technologies such as the project method, role-playing games, work technologies should be used. In our opinion, problematic tasks are of particular importance, thanks to their analysis, students try to understand the essence of events, which leads to a deeper understanding of themselves, and understanding themselves, knowing their needs, students have an eye for self-development they want more.

The organizational and activity component includes the integration of different forms of teaching, which helps to form creativity and use more creative tasks aimed at eliminating stereotypes of students.

The content component includes educational activities (using the methods described above, quality selection of material that contributes to the achievement of integral course goals) and extracurricular activities (intercultural interaction, independent study of the material).

The following main principles of the integrative approach to foreign language teaching can be distinguished:

- the principle of civility;
- the principle of creativity;
- the principle of orientation towards self-development and self-education;
- principle of variability;
- principle of multicultural self-determination and self-awareness of the individual;
- principle of tolerance;
- principle of communication of cultures.

Among the main goals of the integrative approach to foreign language teaching, it seems important to highlight the following:

- formation of a holistic picture of the world (students understand the purpose of studying objects more deeply, understand the connection between them, thus the motivation for the learning process increases);
- formation of new skills due to the interconnection of the system with elements of different systems and mutual enrichment (due to this, the opportunities of students are expanding);

- formation of a new type of person free from stereotypes and free to choose actions, which is important in connection with the formation of a person ready for constructive intercultural communication;
- forming a tolerant person, which is one of the priority tasks of the education system at this stage of society's development;
- forming a creative person who is ready to look for solutions in non-standard situations (by creating problematic situations);
- formation of moral values of students (introduction of moral material);
- formation of basic competencies (communicative, social-cultural, educational and cognitive).

The result of using an integrative approach in teaching a foreign language is as follows: acceleration of the educational process, systematization of educational and cognitive activities, formation of basic competencies, formation of a person ready for effective intercultural communication, formation of professional skills of students, comprehensive development of the personality, forming the variability of thinking, forming a new type of student personality.

As a result of the analysis of scientific research literature, we identified three groups of methods in foreign language teaching:

- cognitive-research (research, method of formation of cultural self-determination, abstracts, project method);
- communicative-problematic (culturally-oriented discussions of a problematic nature, culturally-oriented role-playing games);
- problem search (use of information technologies: slide presentations, web quests, blogs).

Our research in the practice of teaching a foreign language to students confirms the effectiveness of the selected methods. Thus, we came to the conclusion that the use of this set of methods makes it possible to fulfill all the tasks and goals of integrative education.

Based on the integrative approach, the working principles of the model developed for the development of students' readiness for professional and innovative activities were determined. General principles include those that reflect the objective requirements for the development of students' readiness for professional and innovative activities: systematization, hierarchy, development. The principle of systematization allows considering the interrelationships of all components of the model as a unit. The principle of hierarchy ensures the organization of model elements based on the subordination of lower-level elements to higher-level elements. The principle of development implies a qualitative change in the characteristics of the student's personality.

Conclusion:

In general, many factors affect the effectiveness of professional and innovative activities. These are the acquisition of theoretical knowledge of the taught subject; it is clearly indicated which problems the student should study during independent activity; list of recommended literature; recommendations regarding the methods by which the student should study the problem; the type and criteria of assessment should be clearly indicated. We believe that the achieved results (principles) create ample opportunities to develop the scientific and methodological foundations of preparing students for professional and innovative activities.

Thus, thanks to the integrative approach, there is an opportunity for self-awareness and self-determination of the student's personality. The thinking of students who are used to thinking according to the same scheme will change. It should also be noted that it is especially important to activate the moral sphere of consciousness. By combining knowledge, it is possible to form new educational courses that meet the needs of modern society.

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